

Acknowledgement

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Diphenyl Sulphoxide by Chloramine-B in Aqueous Acid Medium

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THE oxidation kinetics of diphenyl sulphoxide with chloramine-B have been studied in aqueous acetic acid medium. The reaction involves an initial slow step followed by a rapid one, indicating that the reaction follows complicated kinetics.

Experimental

Diphenyl sulphoxide was prepared by the Friedel-Crafts reaction of benzene with thionyl chloride¹. Chloramine-B (CAB) (sodium *N*-chlorobenzenesulphonamide) was prepared by partial chlorination of benzenesulphonamide². Sodium

sulphate was employed to maintain the ionic strength.

The kinetic studies were carried out in 50% (v/v) aqueous acetic acid at an ionic strength of 0.23 mol dm⁻³ under pseudo-first order conditions (at 35±0.5°). The reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted CAB iodometrically.

The stoichiometry (1 : 1) of the oxidation was determined with varying amounts of oxidant in excess over the substrate. The products were detected by tlc.

Results and Discussion

The order with respect to oxidant (1.7) was found out by half-life method³. For all the runs, rates were determined when 40% of the reaction was over and from that rate constant was calculated. The fairly constant *k* values confirm the fractional order with respect to oxidant (Table 1). The rate of the reaction was independent of [sulphoxide]. The *k* values are fairly constant within the limits of experimental error (Table 1). The rate increased with increase in [Acid] and the plot of log *k* vs log [H⁺] was linear with a gradient 1.82 (*r*, 0.997).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF REACTANTS CONCENTRATION ON RATE OF OXIDATION OF DIPHENYL SULPHOXIDE BY CHLORAMINE-B (CAB)

Medium : Aqueous acetic acid (1 : 1, v/v), [H⁺]=0.95 mol dm⁻³, Temp.=308 K

[Sulphoxide] ₀ × 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	[CAB] ₀ × 10 ² mol dm ⁻³	<i>k</i> × 10 ² s	AcOH* %	<i>k</i> × 10 ² s
3.44	0.93	6.8	50	6.9
3.44	1.63	6.9	55	7.6
3.44	1.85	6.2	60	9.7
3.44	2.32	6.6	65	13.5
3.44	2.78	6.2	10μ ^a (mol dm ⁻²)	
3.44	3.70	6.7		
1.98	1.63	6.4	1.2	8.5
2.75	1.63	6.3	2.3	6.3
4.13	1.63	6.5	3.5	5.9
5.50	1.63	7.2	4.7	5.1
6.88	1.63	6.8		

^a[CAB]₀ = 1.63 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³; [Sulphoxide]₀ = 3.44 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³.

The rate increased with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium (Table 1). The plot of log *k* vs 1/*D* was linear with a positive slope, indicating positive ion-dipole interactions. Addition of one of the reaction products benzenesulphonamide (BSA) had no effect on the rate (Table 1). The rates decreased with the increase in ionic strength of the medium (Table 1). Addition of Cl⁻ increased the rate very sharply. The reaction was too fast and it could not be followed.

The reaction was studied at four different temperatures 35, 40, 42.5 and 45°. The values of

activation parameters are $E_a=67.7$ kJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta H^\ddagger=65.1$ kJ mol⁻¹ and $\Delta S^\ddagger=-56$ JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹. The possibility of radical involvement in the reaction was ruled out as the addition of acrylamide in the reaction mixture did not initiate polymerisation. It was also confirmed by low value of ΔS^\ddagger .

The possible oxidising species in acidified CAB solution are RNHCl, RNCl₂, HOCl, Cl₂ and H₂OCl⁺. Bishop and Jennings first approximation calculations on 0.1 M solutions of CAT shows that the concentration of RNHCl is high at pH 0–3. Considering the experimental conditions and observations the most probable mechanistic pathway is given below.

The Scheme leads to the rate law,

$$-d[\text{CAB}]/dt = k'_2 [\text{RNH}_2\text{Cl}^+]^2$$

After omitting the higher terms,

$$-d[\text{CAB}]/dt = \frac{k'_2 K_2^2 [\text{CAB}]_0^2 [\text{H}^+]^2}{1 + 2K_1 [\text{CAB}]_0 + 2K_1 [\text{H}^+]}$$

The rate law accords well with the kinetic orders in oxidant, substrate and acid.

Quinlan-Amis equation^{4, 5} for ion-dipolar molecule reaction is in accordance with the effect of ionic strength on the reaction rate. In the presence of Cl⁻, the reaction is very fast. It may be due to the formation of Cl₂,

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Mechanism of Oxidation of Aromatic Amine by Periodate. Further Supporting Evidence

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THE mechanism of oxidation of aromatic amine has been studied using various oxidants¹, but no conclusive mechanism has yet emerged and those available are at variance with each other. The nature of the product vary from oxidant to oxidant, hence to arrive at a reasonable conclusion, sufficient data covering a wide variety of substrates are required.

We have carried out a detailed kinetic study on the oxidation of 2,5-dimethylaniline by periodate ion in 2.5% (v/v) acetic acid–water. The reaction rate decreased with decreased dielectric constant and increased ionic strength of the medium. The reaction was pH-dependent. The main oxidation product was confirmed to be 2,5-dimethyl-*p*-benzoquinone². The stoichiometry of the reaction was found to be 2 : 1 (oxidant : substrate). On the basis of kinetic and non-kinetic evidences we proposed³ a bimolecular interaction mechanism with the rate-limiting formation for an activated complex (A) possessing a positively charged nitrogen in direct conjugation with the aromatic ring (structure A, Scheme 1). Subsequently, to confirm the existence of such a species, we have studied periodate oxidation of a number of mono substituted anilines (X–C₆H₄NH₂; X=H, *p*-Cl, *p*-Br, *p*-I, *p*-Me, *p*-OMe and *p*-OEt) under similar conditions with a view to evaluate electronic substituent effect.

The concentration range used for the amine³ and the oxidant were 1.0–1.5 × 10⁻³ and 1.0–1.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ respectively. However, in the case of *p*-methoxy- and *p*-ethoxyanilines much lower concentration of the reactants (amine and oxidant, 3.0 × 10⁻³ and 3.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ respectively) was used. The reaction was followed at the λ_{max} of the principal product (Table 1) on a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 100 spectrophotometer. Guggenheim and Swinbourne methods⁴ were not applicable for calculation of rate constant. Hence initial rate, $(dA/dt)_i$, calculated by plane mirror method⁵ was taken as the first order rate constant, k_1 . A plot of $\log k_2$ (k_2 =second order rate constant) versus σ^+ shows that substituents having lone-pair of electron, such as *p*-Cl, *p*-Br, *p*-I, *p*-OMe, exhibit a reasonably good linear relationship ($\rho = -2.3$). Such group effectively stabilise the activated complex by direct resonance interaction. In the case of *p*-Me group, only a weak hyperconjugative effect is operating. The slight deviation observed in this case may not